

Robust Resource Management for Mission-Critical In-Factory Subnetworks under External Interference

Saeed Hakimi⁽¹⁾, K. Pavan Srinath⁽²⁾, Saeed Bagherinejad⁽¹⁾, Ramoni Adeogun⁽¹⁾,
Gilberto Berardinelli⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾Department of Electronic Systems, Aalborg University, Denmark

⁽²⁾Nokia Bell Labs, Nozay, France

⁽¹⁾{sachak, sbag, ra, gb}@es.aau.dk

⁽²⁾pavan.koteshwar_srinath@nokia-bell-labs.com

Abstract—The concept of subnetworks has been recently identified as a key component of 6G, enabling mission-critical services with hyper-reliability. In this paper, we address the challenges posed by both inter-subnetwork interference and external interference in hyper-dense and dynamic industrial environments. We focus on in-factory subnetworks for industrial wireless control applications and propose an advanced frequency-power resource allocation scheme using Gradient Descent-based Resource Allocation (GDRA). The proposed GDRA scheme efficiently mitigates interference while optimizing resource allocation. We evaluate the performance of the proposed scheme and compare it with state-of-the-art approaches, demonstrating significant improvements in spectral efficiency and reliability.

Index Terms—In-factory subnetworks, gradient descent, mission-critical, resource allocation, 6G

I. INTRODUCTION

Future sixth-generation (6G) wireless networks are expected to support a diverse range of services and use cases, from high-data-rate, delay-sensitive eXtended Reality (XR) applications to mission critical industrial automation and control systems. The communication requirements for these services could be extremely demanding, placing significant strain on wireless networks and surpassing the capabilities of fifth-generation (5G) systems. Meeting these demands will require advancements in network architecture and resource allocation techniques [1].

In-X subnetworks have been proposed as a potential solution to meet these stringent requirements [2]. These subnetworks focus on enabling highly specialized small cells that provide connectivity to devices within close proximity to an access point (AP), with applications in industrial robotics and automation modules. The APs are assumed to manage communications within the sub-network while also offering mobile-edge computing capabilities for processing sub-network data, such as motion, force/torque, and position control. Due to the potentially high deployment density of subnetworks, their performance is primarily constrained by high interference levels. This necessitates the design of novel radio resource management (RRM) algorithms tailored to the

unique requirements of in-X subnetworks. Several research efforts have explored this area [3]–[9]. In [3], the performance of industrial subnetworks is evaluated under various centralized and distributed sub-band allocation algorithms, considering an adaptive packet repetition scheme. A multi-agent Q-learning framework is employed in [4] to derive a distributed sub-band allocation policy that relies on limited signaling between subnetworks. The authors of [5] and [7] propose similar sequential iterative algorithms for sub-band allocation and power control, respectively, which will be discussed in detail in this article. In [6], a graph neural network-based power control algorithm is designed to maximize sum spectral efficiency (SE) under different assumptions regarding available information. Additionally, in [8], a sub-band allocation algorithm based on deep neural networks is proposed to maximize the number of satisfied subnetworks at each allocation instance while considering different quality of service (QoS) requirements. For autonomous subnetworks, a dynamic sub-band allocation algorithm is introduced in [9], aiming to minimize the number of utilized sub-bands and reduce sub-network reconfiguration at each transmission interval.

Most existing research on RRM for in-X subnetworks assumes no external interference, which is often unrealistic. In practice, subnetworks face two types of interference: inter-subnetwork interference, caused by neighboring subnetworks operating within the same system, and external interference, originating from other radio technologies coexisting in the same area and sharing the same frequency spectrum. In this work, we assume that the subnetworks are coordinated and controlled by a centralized 6G base station, enabling efficient management of inter-subnetwork interference through coordinated resource allocation. Unlike this controllable interference, external interference is unpredictable and beyond the control of the network operator. To address these challenges, this paper integrates external interference awareness into radio resource management, enhancing the reliability and robustness of in-X subnetworks. Specifically, we investigate the joint sub-band allocation and power control problem for densely deployed in-factory subnetworks (InF-Ss) under external interference. The main contributions are as follows:

- To solve the joint sub-band and power control problem in

This research is supported by the HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-03, 6G-SHINE project (Grant Agreement No. 101095738) and the HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-02, CENTRIC project (Grant Agreement No. 101096379).

the presence of external interference, we design a novel Gradient Descent-based Resource Allocation (GDRA) algorithm that maximizes the minimum SE while ensuring all resource constraints are met.

- We enhance two state-of-the-art (SoA) algorithms, Sequential Iterative Sub-band Allocation (SISA) and Sequential Iterative Power Allocation (SIPA), to make them external interference-aware. These modifications allow fair performance comparisons and demonstrate the effectiveness of interference-aware RRM strategies.
- We evaluate the proposed scheme through extensive simulations, showing that it outperforms SoA methods under the same deployment conditions, achieving superior reliability and robustness.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the system model and problem formulation. Section III details the proposed RRM solution. Section IV presents the performance evaluation. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

We consider a factory environment with a centralized radio manager (CRM) entity that efficiently manages radio resources across multiple mobile, densely deployed short-range cells (InF-Ss), each consisting of a central node acting as both AP and edge processor for devices within its subnetwork. The system architecture is illustrated in Fig. 1. The factory consists of N independent InF-Ss, denoted by the set $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, distributed over an area of $D \times D$ (m²). Each AP operates within a circular coverage area of radius R , ensuring that devices are located at distances between d_{\min} and R from the AP. This configuration maintains a minimum proximity d_{\min} while keeping devices within the AP's communication range. The available spectrum is divided into sub-bands, denoted by $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$, which are shared among all devices within the factory. Each subnetwork serves a single device, fully utilizing its assigned sub-band for transmission. The subnetworks move along preplanned trajectories, with their velocities represented as $\mathbf{v} = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_N\}$.

External interference is modeled as originating from one or more mobile interference sources, denoted by $\mathcal{I} = \{I_1, I_2, \dots, I_J\}$, which operate in the same frequency band as the InF-Ss and follow predefined trajectories within the factory environment. Each sub-band experiences independent external interference governed by a Poisson traffic model, where packet arrivals follow a Poisson process with an average arrival rate λ . During each time step, interference is activated in a sub-band if at least one packet arrives. When interference is active, the transmit interference power remains constant for each active event, regardless of the number of arriving packets. The external interference power level is defined relative to the maximum transmission power as:

$$I_{\text{ext(dB)}} = P_{\text{max(dB)}} + \alpha, \quad (1)$$

where α is the interference power ratio in dB, representing the relative power level of the external interferers compared to the maximum transmission power of the devices in the

subnetworks. Given the short-range operations in in-factory environments, both devices and APs operate at comparable power levels. The received interference power varies depending on the distance between the APs and the interferers, as well as the prevailing channel conditions.

We assume that external interference is accurately detected and measured using periodic reference sequences and scheduled silent slots. Each subnetwork transmits sounding reference signals for neighboring subnetworks to estimate the channel state information (CSI) and measure interference. To complement this, scheduled silent slots allow the APs to measure external interference without contamination from desired signals. During these silent slots, all subnetworks remain silent, ensuring that any received signal at the APs originates solely from external interference sources. These measurements, reported to the CRM via dedicated backhaul channels, remain valid for subsequent transmissions under the assumption of limited temporal variations in channel conditions and interference. With this detection mechanism in place, we focus on analyzing the impact of external interference on RRM and evaluating the robustness of our designed RRM algorithms in maintaining In-FS performance and reliability.

The primary objective is to develop a resource allocation strategy that jointly optimizes sub-band allocation and power control to minimize the outage probability across all subnetworks while meeting a target SE SE_{target} . This target SE ensures minimum QoS for mission-critical applications, maintaining reliable communication and data throughput under interference. Sub-band allocation is denoted by $a_n^k \in \{0, 1\}$ and specifies whether subnetwork n transmits on sub-band k ($a_n^k = 1$ for active transmission). These variables are adjusted based on the CSI, \mathbf{H} . Each subnetwork is constrained to use a single sub-band, i.e., $\sum_{k=1}^K a_n^k = 1$. The transmit power of subnetwork n is denoted by P_n , and is modeled as a continuous variable with a constraint P_{max} , thus offering greater flexibility compared to discrete power levels.

The SE achieved by subnetwork n on sub-band k is expressed as:

$$SE_n^k = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{h_{n,n}^k a_n^k P_n}{\gamma_{m,n}^2 + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{n\}} h_{m,n}^k a_m^k P_m + I_n^k} \right), \quad (2)$$

where $h_{n,n}^k$ represents the desired channel link for subnetwork n at sub-band k , $\sum_{m \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{n\}} h_{m,n}^k a_m^k P_m$ is the interference from other subnetworks to AP n in sub-band k , $I_n^k(t)$ is the external interference power at AP n over sub-band k and $\gamma_{m,n}^2$ is the receiver noise power, calculated as:

$$\gamma_{m,n}^2 = 10^{\frac{-174 + \text{NF} + 10 \log_{10}(W_k)}{10}}, \quad (3)$$

where W_k denotes the sub-band bandwidth (in Hz), and NF represents the receiver noise figure (in dB).

The optimization problem for sub-band allocation and

Fig. 1. System model illustrating the deployment of InF-Ss.

power control is formulated as:

$$\max_{\{a_n^k, p_n\}} \min_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{SE}_n^k, \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } a_n^k \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (4b)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} a_n^k = 1, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (4c)$$

$$0 \leq p_n \leq P_{\max}, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (4d)$$

This mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) problem is non-convex, which means a unique solution may not exist or may be computationally impractical to obtain. Therefore, the goal is to find a feasible sub-optimal solution.

III. RRM IN THE PRESENCE OF EXTERNAL INTERFERENCE

In this section, we introduce our proposed GDRA algorithm, specifically designed to jointly optimize sub-band and power allocation in the presence of external interference. Additionally, we modify two SoA algorithms, namely SISA and SIPA, to incorporate external interference awareness.

A. Gradient Descent-based Resource Allocation Algorithm

The detailed steps of the GDRA algorithm are presented in Algorithm 1. The GDRA algorithm employs a two-stage optimization process to jointly optimize sub-band allocation and power control. In the first stage, we relax the single sub-band constraint and suppose that P_n^k is the power on sub-band k for subnetwork n with $\sum_{k=1}^K P_n^k \leq P_{\max}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$. The purpose of this stage is to allow the algorithm to allocate powers, i.e., assign values to P_n^k , with the goal of optimizing the objective given in (4a) and to identify which of the sub-bands contributes the most to the SE for each sub-network. After this stage, each subnetwork selects its most favorable sub-band to ensure single sub-band allocation, as detailed in Algorithm 1. In the algorithm, a softmax function is used to distribute the power across the K sub-bands, with a low temperature parameter τ producing near one-hot outputs while remaining differentiable. The sigmoid function keeps power levels within the maximum level. The loss function is given by $\mathcal{L} = -\min_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \text{SE}_n^k$. Notably, this first stage can also be used independently as a sub-band allocation strategy when combined with maximum transmit power, forming the (Gradient Descent-based Sub-band Allocation) GDSA-maxPower approach evaluated in Section IV.

Algorithm 1 GDRA Algorithm for Joint Sub-band Allocation and Power Control

Input: Channel gains matrix H of size (B, K, N, N) , External interference power I of size (B, K, N) , n_{epoch} , Softmax temperature τ , Maximum transmit power P_{\max}
Initialize: Power variable $\rho^{(0)}$ and selection variable $\theta^{(0)}$ as zero matrices of size (B, K, N)

Stage 1: Sub-band Selection

- 1: **for** $l = 1$ to n_{epoch} **do**
- 2: **for** $b = 1$ to B **do**
- 3: $P \leftarrow P_{\max} \cdot \sigma(\rho^{(l-1)}) \cdot \text{Softmax}\left(\frac{\theta^{(l-1)}}{\tau}\right)$
- 4: Calculate SE using Eq. (2)
- 5: Formulate objective function as in Eq. (4a)
- 6: Update $(\rho^{(l)}, \theta^{(l)}) \leftarrow \text{Adam}(\nabla_{\rho, \theta} \mathcal{L}^{(l-1)})$
- 7: $k^*(n) \leftarrow \arg \max_k \text{SE}_n^k$ \triangleright Select sub-band with max SE

Stage 2: Power Control with Fixed Sub-band Selection

- 8: $M \leftarrow \mathbb{1}\{k = k^*(n)\}$ \triangleright One-hot encoded mask
 - 9: **for** $l = 1$ to n_{epoch} **do**
 - 10: **for** $b = 1$ to B **do**
 - 11: $P \leftarrow P_{\max} \cdot \sigma(\rho^{(l-1)}) \cdot M$
 - 12: Calculate SE using Eq. (2)
 - 13: Formulate objective function for power control as in Eq. (4a)
 - 14: $p^{(l)} \leftarrow \text{Adam}(\nabla_{\rho} \mathcal{L}^{(l-1)})$
 - 15: $P^{(l)} \leftarrow P_{\max} \cdot \frac{P}{\max(P)}$ \triangleright Adjust power to meet constraints
- Output:** Optimized power control $P^{(l)}$ and sub-band allocation $k^*(n)$

The second stage focuses on optimizing power control for the fixed sub-bands identified in the first stage. The gradient descent is performed iteratively to obtain power values satisfying the constraint in (4d) using Adam optimizer.

GDRA decouples the sub-band allocation and power control tasks, optimizing them sequentially to improve computational efficiency. The use of softmax and sigmoid functions provides a differentiable approximation, enabling end-to-end optimization through gradient descent.

B. Modified SISA-SIPA Algorithm

Now, we discuss the necessary modifications for two SoA algorithms: SISA, proposed in [5], and SIPA, introduced in [7]. These algorithms minimize the sum Interference-to-Signal Ratio (ISR) of the entire network under the assumption of no external interference. However, since an external interference source is now present, the algorithms must be adapted to account for this additional interference.

1) External-Interference-Aware SISA

We start with SISA, a sequential and iterative sub-band allocation algorithm, whose details can be found in [5]. Here, we focus only on the modifications to this algorithm. The algorithm begins with an arbitrary sub-band allocation and then iteratively updates it by examining subnetworks one by one. Each sub-network selects the sub-band that minimizes the sum

mutual ISR, assuming the allocations of other subnetworks remain fixed. More precisely, we denote the ISR from the m -th sub-network to the n -th sub-network over the k -th sub-band as $W_{nm}^k = \frac{\omega_{nm}^k}{\omega_n^k}$, where ω_{nm}^k and ω_n^k represent the channel gain powers of the interfering and desired channels, respectively. Then, at the d -th iteration, the sub-band allocation is carried out based on the following criterion:

$$k^* = \arg \min_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{A}_k^d} (W_{nm}^k + W_{mn}^k), \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{A}_k^d denotes the set of subnetworks to which the k -th sub-band has been allocated after $d - 1$ selections. After selecting a sub-band, the algorithm proceeds to the next sub-network and continues until the selection process has been performed L times for all subnetworks. As seen in (5), SISA minimizes the mutual ISR, i.e., both the ISR from other subnetworks to the intended sub-network and the ISR from the intended sub-network to others, ensuring a fairer allocation. By incorporating the external interference power over the n -th sub-network, we update the sub-band selection criterion of SISA as follows:

$$k^* = \arg \min_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{A}_k^d} (W_{nm}^k + W_{mn}^k) + W_{n,\text{ext}}^k, \quad (6)$$

where $W_{n,\text{ext}}^k = \frac{I_n^k}{\omega_n^k}$ represents the ISR from external interference. This additional term enables the algorithm to account for external interference, favoring sub-bands with lower or no interference.

2) External-Interference-Aware SIPA

SIPA, similar to SISA, follows a sequential and iterative approach for Tx power control using discrete power levels. More specifically, SIPA starts with random Tx power levels selected from the set of Tx power levels, i.e., \mathcal{P} , and iterates through the subnetworks one by one, choosing the power level that minimizes the mutual ISR while keeping the Tx power levels of the other subnetworks fixed. The selection criterion of SIPA must be revised to account for external interference, resulting in:

$$\phi_n^{(d)}(P) = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{A}_k} \left(\frac{[\mathbf{P}^{(d-1)}]_m}{P} W_{nm}^k + \frac{P}{[\mathbf{P}^{(d-1)}]_m} W_{mn}^k \right) + \frac{1}{P} W_{n,\text{ext}}^k, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{P}^{(d-1)}$ represents the vector of selected power levels for the subnetworks after $d - 1$ iterations. The additional term in (7), compared to the standard SIPA algorithm, accounts for external interference and encourages the selection of higher Tx power levels. Algorithm 2 summarizes the procedure of the modified SIPA for the subnetworks in the k -th sub-band, which runs until the Tx power of each sub-network is updated L times, similar to SISA.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed GDRA algorithm for joint sub-band allocation and power control, comparing it with SoA algorithms, including the modified

Algorithm 2 External-Interference-Aware SIPA for k -th sub-band

Input:

\mathcal{A}_k , and $W_{nm}^k, \forall n, m \in \mathcal{A}_k$,
 \mathcal{P} , the discrete set of Tx powers.

Initialize: $P_n^{(0)}$ from the set \mathcal{P} .

- 1: **for** $l = 1$ to L **do**
- 2: **for** $n = 1$ to N **do**
- 3: Set iteration number: $d = N(l - 1) + n$
- 4: **for** $P = 1$ to $|\mathcal{P}|$ **do**
- 5: Compute $\phi_n^{(d)}(P)$ using (7).
- 6: $\mathbf{P}^{(d)} = \mathbf{P}^{(d-1)}$
- 7: $[\mathbf{P}^{(d)}]_n = \mathcal{P} \left(\arg \min_P \phi_n^{(d)}(P) \right)$

Output: power control $\mathbf{P}^{(d)}$, where $d = LN$.

SISA and SIPA algorithms as benchmarks. To provide a more comprehensive assessment of the power control strategies, we also consider two additional approaches: the combination of SISA with maximum transmit power and the proposed GDSA with maximum transmit power.

Simulations were conducted using a cloud computing environment equipped with an AMD EPYC-Rome Processor (40 cores, 40 threads at 2.9 GHz) and an NVIDIA A40 GPU, with 64GB of RAM.

The wireless communication channel model used for the connection between devices and APs follows the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) specifications for in-factory (InF) scenarios [10]. The channel gain between the device in subnetwork m and the AP in subnetwork n is expressed as:

$$h_{m,n} = |g_{m,n}|^2 \cdot \Gamma_{m,n} \cdot \psi_{m,n}, \quad (8)$$

where $g_{m,n}$ represents the small-scale fading component, modeled as a Rayleigh distributed random variable. $\Gamma_{m,n}$ denotes the path loss, calculated using the 3GPP model for dense clutter with low base station height (DL) [10]. $\psi_{m,n}$ represents the correlated shadowing effect, modeled as a stationary isotropic Gaussian random field over the factory area, capturing the spatial correlation across subnetwork links [11].

The external interference model is described in detail in Section II. We consider one mobile source of external interference, which generates independent interference on different sub-bands. The simulation parameters used in the experiments are summarized in Table I, except in cases where specific parameter variations are explicitly mentioned to evaluate their impact on performance.

The main performance metric considered is the outage probability, defined as the probability that the achieved SE is lower than the target SE, $\text{SE}_{\text{target}}$.

Fig. 2 illustrates the outage probability of individual links across all subnetworks as a function of the target SE, $\text{SE}_{\text{target}}$. The performance of the proposed GDRA and GDSA algorithms is compared against the benchmark methods: SISA-SIPA and SISA-maxPower under three scenarios: *No Interference*, *Interference-Unaware*, and *Interference-Aware*. In the *No External Interference* scenario, only inter-subnetwork

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Factory area, $D \times D$	20 m \times 20 m
Number of subnetworks, N	20
Number of sub-bands, K	4
Subnetwork radius, R	0.5 m
Number of devices per subnetwork	1
Minimum distance between APs	1 m
Device to AP minimum distance, d_{min}	0.3 m
Shadowing standard deviation, σ_s	4 dB
DL clutter density, τ , clutter size, d_s	0.6, 2
De-correlation distance, d_c	5 m
Maximum transmit power, P_{max}	0 dBm
Interference power ratio, α	-20 dB
Number of sub-bands with active interference, K_{intf}	2
Average arrival rate for external interference, λ	0.3
Sounding reference signal period, Δt	100 ms
Maximum velocity of InF-S and External interferer, v_{max}	10 m/s
Sub-band bandwidth, W_k	30 MHz
Center frequency, f_c	10 GHz
Noise figure, NF	5 dB
Temperature parameter for softmax, τ	0.001
Batch size, B	20000
Number of epochs	1000

Fig. 2. Outage probability of individual links across all subnetworks, under three scenarios: No Interference, Interference-Unaware, and Interference-Aware.

interference is present. The *External Interference-Unaware* scenario includes external interference from sources outside the considered subnetworks. However, in this scenario, the resource allocation algorithms are unaware of the presence of external interference and, therefore, do not adapt their strategies to mitigate it. Conversely, the *External Interference-Aware* scenario incorporates knowledge of external interference into the resource allocation process.

In the *No Interference* scenario, all algorithms achieve low outage probabilities across the entire range of SE_{target} , demonstrating effective inter-subnetwork interference management. In the *Interference-Unaware* scenario, the outage probability significantly increases, particularly at higher SE_{target} , due to the lack of adaptation to external interference. In the *Interference-Aware* scenario, all algorithms show improved performance compared to the *Interference-Unaware* case, but GDRA consistently outperforms all others. For example, at $SE_{target} = 5$, the outage probability for GDRA is 0.008, compared to 0.077 for the SISA-SIPA, representing around 90% reduction in outage probability.

Fig. 3. CDF of the average SE across all subnetworks, under two scenarios: Interference-Unaware and Interference-Aware.

Fig. 3 presents the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the average SE across all subnetworks, comparing the proposed algorithms with the benchmark methods. Notably, while power control optimization improves outage probability, maximum transmit power achieves better performance at higher percentiles for both the benchmark and proposed methods.

Additionally, gradient descent-based algorithms consistently demonstrate superior performance, particularly in interference-aware scenarios. Consequently, the proposed algorithm enhances not only mission-critical communication systems but also other scenarios requiring efficient spectral utilization.

Fig. 4 compares the outage probability of the algorithms under varying levels of external interference power. GDRA consistently achieves the lowest outage probability. Notably, at $SE_{target} = 3$ bps/Hz, GDRA guarantees 99% reliability, making it suitable for critical use cases, while the benchmarks exhibit an outage probability of 25%, highlighting a significant performance advantage. At lower interference power levels, GDRA outperforms GDSA-maxPower due to its optimized power control strategy. However, as the external interference power approaches the maximum transmission power P_{max} , the performance of GDRA converges with GDSA-maxPower, indicating that power optimization becomes less effective under high interference conditions, where performance is primarily limited by the interference power itself.

Fig. 5 analyzes the impact of interference activation on different numbers of sub-bands. As the number of interfered sub-bands, K_{intf} increases, the outage probability rises for all algorithms, reflecting the increased interference burden. However, GDRA consistently maintains a lower outage probability compared to SISA-SIPA, showcasing its effective interference management and adaptive resource allocation strategy. The performance gap between GDRA and SISA-SIPA widens as more sub-bands are affected, emphasizing the adaptability of GDRA in dynamically changing interference scenarios.

Fig. 6 presents the CDF of the transmit powers across all subnetworks. The results reveal that all algorithms tend to utilize higher transmit power levels to maintain SE, particularly under high external interference conditions. As the interference power increases, all algorithms exhibit a general shift towards

Fig. 4. Outage probability of individual links across all subnetworks, under varying levels of external interference power.

Fig. 5. Outage probability of individual links across all subnetworks, under scenarios with no interference and with interference activated on 1, 2, and 3 sub-bands.

higher transmit powers.

While the asymptotic complexity of SISA, SIPA, and GDRA simplifies to $O(KN^2)$ with constant parameters [5]–[7], GDRA stands out for its parallelizability and GPU-optimized design, enabling faster processing and better resource utilization. Table II shows the execution time per sample for GDRA at different batch sizes and for SISA-SIPA, which are processed sequentially and cannot natively leverage batch processing. As the batch size increases, GDRA achieves significantly lower execution time per sample, demonstrating its computational efficiency of batch processing.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we investigated the impact of external interference on RRM for dense industrial subnetworks. We proposed a joint sub-band allocation and power control scheme using the GDRA algorithm, which effectively mitigates both inter-subnetwork and external interference. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed GDRA algorithm outperforms state-of-the-art methods, achieving superior SE and reliability under various interference scenarios. For instance, under external interference conditions where the interference power is 20 dB below the maximum transmission power of the devices and is active on two sub-bands, the GDRA algorithm achieves approximately 90% reduction in outage probability at a target SE of 5 bps/Hz compared to benchmark methods. These

Fig. 6. CDF of transmit powers across all subnetworks, under varying levels of external interference power.

TABLE II
EXECUTION TIME PER SAMPLE FOR DIFFERENT BATCH SIZES AND ALGORITHMS

Algorithm	Batch Size	Execution Time (s)
GDRA	200	0.1925
GDRA	2000	0.0509
GDRA	20000	0.0213
SISA-SIPA	-	0.0243

findings highlight the importance of interference awareness for maintaining reliable communication in dense industrial environments.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Viswanathan and P. E. Mogensen, “Communications in the 6G Era,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 57 063–57 074, 2020.
- [2] G. Berardinelli, P. Baracca, R. O. Adeogun, S. R. Khosravirad, F. Schaich, K. Upadhyay, D. Li, T. Tao, H. Viswanathan, and P. Mogensen, “Extreme communication in 6G: Vision and challenges for ‘in-X’ subnetworks,” *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 2, pp. 2516–2535, 2021.
- [3] R. Adeogun, G. Berardinelli, and P. E. Mogensen, “Enhanced Interference Management for 6G in-X Subnetworks,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 45 784–45 798, 2022.
- [4] R. Adeogun and G. Berardinelli, “Multi-Agent Dynamic Resource Allocation in 6G in-X Subnetworks with Limited Sensing Information,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 13, p. 5062, 2022.
- [5] D. Li, S. R. Khosravirad, T. Tao, and P. Baracca, “Advanced Frequency Resource Allocation for Industrial Wireless Control in 6G Subnetworks,” in *2023 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [6] D. Abode, R. Adeogun, and G. Berardinelli, “Power Control for 6G In-Factory Subnetworks With Partial Channel Information Using Graph Neural Networks,” *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 5, pp. 3120–3135, 2024.
- [7] D. Li, S. R. Khosravirad, T. Tao, P. Baracca, and P. Wen, “Power Allocation for 6G Sub-Networks in Industrial Wireless Control,” in *2024 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [8] S. Hakimi, R. Adeogun, and G. Berardinelli, “Rate-conforming Sub-band Allocation for In-factory Subnetworks: A Deep Neural Network Approach,” in *2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 729–734.
- [9] V. T. Haider, R. Pries, W. Kellerer, and F. Mehmeti, “Dynamic Frequency Planning for Autonomous Mobile 6G in-X Subnetworks,” 2025.
- [10] 3GPP, “Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz,” 2018.
- [11] S. Lu, J. May, and R. J. Haines, “Effects of Correlated Shadowing Modeling on Performance Evaluation of Wireless Sensor Networks,” in *2015 IEEE 82nd Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2015-Fall)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 1–5.